

Report Appendices

JUNE 2025

Table of Contents

Appendix 1: Intervention pipeline	2
Background.....	2
Analytical Framework	5
Case Examples.....	10
PM+ (Psychological intervention)	10
Social intervention (Cash transfers)	12
Appendix 2: Project team and advisory group	14
Project Team.....	14
Global Advisory Board Members	15
Appendix 3: Further methodological detail for landscape map	17
Evidence review	18
Stakeholder perspectives of the field	21
PLE perspectives of the field.....	21
Appendix 4: Priority-setting using Delphi like process	22
Appendix 5: Pipeline progression by target conditions	24
Psychological interventions.....	24
Psychosocial interventions	25
Social interventions	25
Appendix 6: Overview of psychological, psychosocial, and social interventions against priority setting criteria	26

Appendix 1: Intervention pipeline

Background

While development pipelines are well documented for pharmaceuticals¹ or medical devices and assistive products, this is less common for development processes for psychological and social interventions. A development pipeline refers to the routine processes and expectations around how an intervention is and should be developed to allow for intervention access at scale. Descriptions of how psychological and social interventions are developed for mental health outcomes are relatively scarce across global literature², with much of what is known shared via anecdotal evidence.

In the classic product pipeline for pharmaceuticals and medical products the emphasis is primarily on ‘active ingredients’ influencing efficacy and effectiveness with attention to delivery mechanisms secondary (the latter typically reflecting well-established, lean pathways of formulation, production, and distribution).

For psychological and social interventions, development generally requires an assessment of both “active ingredients” and feasible and effective means for making them available to target populations. There will typically be a plurality of pathways available for intervention delivery, but many will be associated with particular barriers and constraints and heavily influenced by other resources available in that delivery context. Assessing these pathways for delivery requires diverse types of research and evidence to inform intervention development. Across settings there is substantive heterogeneity to be considered in how interventions are delivered.

These observations are reflected in the MRC guidance on intervention development which advocates for the use of implementation science research alongside typical clinical research³. Research designs are often combined in practice, particularly in relation to mental health studies, with many researchers engaging in hybrid research. There are some known hybrid research designs which are therefore worth referencing:

1. **Hybrid Type 1:** Testing a clinical intervention while gathering information on its delivery during the effectiveness trial and/or on its potential for implementation in a real-world situation.
2. **Hybrid Type 2:** Simultaneous testing of a clinical intervention and an implementation intervention/strategy.
3. **Hybrid Type 3:** “Testing an implementation intervention/strategy while observing/gathering information on the clinical intervention and related outcomes.” The authors note that these types of studies are frequently conducted where interventions may be scaled without sufficient effectiveness data, and/or where there it is hypothesised that effectiveness or other important outcomes may change when interventions are provided at scale.

1 DiMasi, J.A., Florez, M.I., Stergiopoulos, S., Peña, Y., Smith, Z., Wilkinson, M., and Getz, K.A. (2020), Development Times and Approval Success Rates for Drugs to Treat Infectious Diseases. *Clin. Pharmacol. Ther.*, 107: 324-332. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpt.1627>

2 van Agteren J, Iasiello M, Ali K, Fassnacht DB, Furber G, Woodyatt L, Howard A, Kyrios M. Using the Intervention Mapping Approach to Develop a Mental Health Intervention: A Case Study on Improving the Reporting Standards for Developing Psychological Interventions. *Front Psychol.* 2021 Oct 5;12:648678. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.648678. PMID: 34675833; PMCID: PMC8524131.

3 Skivington K, Matthews L, Simpson S A, Craig P, Baird J, Blazeby J M et al. A new framework for developing and evaluating complex interventions: update of Medical Research Council guidance *BMJ* 2021; 374 :n2061 doi:10.1136/bmj.n2061

Wellcome has developed a template pipeline for non-pharmacological⁴ (see Figure 1), inspired largely by development in the pharmaceutical sector. As per the points above, several challenges need to be acknowledged with this framing. For example, in many cases psychological interventions are evaluated via studies which simultaneously focus on efficacy/effectiveness and implementation. In this instance, the suggested distinct stages in the pipeline may significantly overlap; or such studies may be used to further iterate or improve an intervention (i.e. return to an earlier stage). Further, regulation is seldom a mandatory step for interventions in this space. Many countries lack formal regulatory processes for interventions – particularly in newly emerging areas of importance such as mental health. Additionally, interventions delivered outside of clinical settings are often not subjected to the same kind of scrutiny and regulation as those offered in clinical settings. One exception to this may be digital interventions, which may be covered by laws governing “medical devices” in some countries or settings. However, this often partly depends on whether the “device” e.g. smartphone app claims to improve wellbeing or is a treatment for a mental disorder.

Figure 1: Template Wellcome pipeline for development of non-pharmacological interventions

⁴ The Wellcome Trust. Understanding the translation pathway in mental health research [version 1; not peer reviewed]. Wellcome Open Res 2024, 9:297 (document) (<https://doi.org/10.21955/wellcomeopenres.1115390.1>)

Some frameworks which more closely consider implementation issues do exist - e.g. see NIH's description of behavioural interventions⁵ (see Figure 2). The NIH model explicitly recognises a stage dedicated to implementation and emphasises iteration and recursiveness. The description provided by the NIH on the framework notes that movement between stages is typical and necessary to ensure interventions reach “maximum level of potency and [are] implementable with a maximum number of individuals in the population.” In contrast frameworks for pharmaceutical or related products, ‘regulatory approval’ does not appear in the NIH framework.

One critique of the NIH framework is that it still assumes a clear separation of research based on different contexts (research or clinical settings vs. communities), when in fact many psychological and psychosocial interventions in particular include multiple components. Both psychological and psychosocial interventions are potentially offered by multiple types of providers (both formal and informal) at various levels. Separation between stages 2-3-4 for example (as per Figure 2) is then challenging and many interventions may iterate repeatedly through these steps.

Figure 2: NIH model for development of behavioural interventions (Source: NIH website)

⁵ See NIH model here: <https://www.nia.nih.gov/research/dbsr/nih-stage-model-behavioral-intervention-development>

Analytical Framework

To review the landscape of psychological and social interventions we clearly require an analytic framework demonstrating the stage of development. However, the preceding discussion cautions against the distortions in analysis introduced if a staged pipeline is assumed that, in practice, does not reflect how interventions are developed and assessed.

For the purposes of this review, therefore, we adopt a framework that acknowledges five core overlapping actions that structure intervention development (see Figure 3). These may follow in sequential order but may also reflect parallel and iterative processes. The framework draws on elements of human centred design and seeks to contextualise these with respect to implementation science approaches and the hybrid research designs described above. This framing is aligned with other existing frameworks that also advocate for more integrated approaches to intervention development and evaluation⁶, including the use of complexity science methods and non-experimental approaches for establishing links between interventions and impacts.

Figure 3: Intervention development pipeline

The framework reflects the common lack of explicit ‘stage gate’ evidentiary thresholds delineating the distinct stages of development for psychological and social interventions. However, five stages can be distinguished in terms of the key actions and outputs specified in Table 1 (of the main report). This framing accommodates the recognition that development is iterative and recursive. Each stage of development informs the next, however, as evidence or learning from one stage becomes available, a return to a previous stage may be possible and desired. Table 1 offers an overview of the stages of the framework and indicates the rationale for each, the actions involved, the stakeholders involved, and outputs and research expected by stage. Case examples for a psychological and a social intervention

⁶ McGinty, E. E., Alegria, M., Beidas, R. S., Braithwaite, J., Kola, L., Leslie, D. L., Moise, N., Mueller, B., Pincus, H. A., Shidhaye, R., Simon, K., Singer, S. J., Stuart, E. A., & Eisenberg, M. D. (2024). The Lancet Psychiatry Commission: transforming mental health implementation research. In *The Lancet Psychiatry* (Vol. 11, Issue 5, pp. 368–396). Elsevier Ltd. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(24\)00040-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(24)00040-3)

are provided in a next section to illustrate how the pipeline can be used to understand the evolution of different interventions.

Further, **the framework does not indicate where intervention development starts**. While ideation is clearly fundamental to the establishment of any intervention, it is important to note that in some cases ideation and adoption may coincide and indeed may precede any (or limited) evidence generation. Particularly in the case of social interventions, adoption (following the passing of legislation or similar) may follow directly after ideation and in the absence of limited evidence generation. Testing may in these circumstances follow rather than precede adoption and inform potential adaptation.

To **operationalise the framework and quantify probabilities of progression between stages**, we propose the calculation of two metrics.

The metrics are:

1. progression from ideation to all other stages (denominator = all interventions at ideation, numerator = all interventions per stage).
2. progression between stages (denominator = interventions at stage a ; numerator = interventions at stage $a+1$).

The first metric can be consistently used across all types of interventions, no matter where an intervention development process starts in practice. While our suggested pipeline framework acknowledges that stages overlap at different points in time, we suggest that the latest stage an intervention is at is consistently used in calculations – in other words, we proceed optimistically that once a stage is entered it is likely to complete. The sample metrics above can still be meaningful when trying to assess progress across the field. In the next section, we illustrate how the above metrics can be used to characterise the state of psychological and social interventions.

Table 1: Details of the development pipeline

Domain	Ideate	Prototype exemplar	Improve and test	Scale	Adopt
Rationale of each stage (ideal case)	Identify a need or opportunity for new intervention depending on currently available/ accessible interventions (or services) and existing research	Determine efficacy and explore some associated outcomes (safety, effectiveness acceptability, feasibility)	Identify optimal implementation mechanisms to achieve high effectiveness. Other outcomes may be studied (efficiency, cost-effectiveness).	Identify best implementation mechanism at scale and determine how this impacts outcome of interest (clinical and other).	Embed interventions into routine practice to ensure wide-spread implementation and access.
Actions by stage	Need and opportunity for a new intervention identified and an intervention mechanism starts to be elaborated.	Intervention actions and mechanisms are decided upon, and intervention undergoes a first stage proof of concept, e.g. an uncontrolled pilot study.	Adapted intervention is tried out in several settings, the implementation itself is studied (ideally including fidelity, costs, provider behaviours) and acceptability, efficacy and effectiveness are revisited. This stage is usually no longer than 2-years but involves controlled studies. The intervention then undergoes further adaptation; usually an intervention manual is then created to allow for replication across other settings.	Adapted intervention is scaled to relevant contexts and populations, usually stepwise and involving capacitation of workforce (in-service training) and further observation of outcomes occurs in practice; outcomes are more varied. This stage longer than adaptation and involves adaptation of existing data systems/creation of new ones to allow M&E of intervention in practice, outside research settings.	Intervention undergoes some level of assessment (by either national health systems, i/NGOs) about whether to fully be adopted into routine service packages and under what conditions. If yes, then routine budgets are set aside to allow for implementation and monitoring, evaluation, and learning. Intervention may be displaced by superior intervention.

Domain	Ideate	Prototype exemplar	Improve and test	Scale	Adopt
Who is involved?	Ideas generated very frequently by health professionals or researchers, occasionally by PLE; private sector ideation more common in MIC/HIC; i/NGO or UN organisation contribution occasionally.	Prototyping frequently conducted by researchers, health professionals, PLE with support also from CBOs, CSOs or i/NGOs, UN organisations.	Most frequently involves health professionals, researchers, and other implementing organisations (CBOs, CSOs, i/NGOs, UN organisations among other sectors – e.g. social care). Policy input sought occasionally.	Most frequently involves implementing organisations and policy makers and/or decision-makers at higher levels in i/NGOs, UN organisations. Researchers less frequently involved.	Policymakers and/or decision-makers at high levels (e.g. international, national, provincial) and funders (e.g. World Bank) for adoption decision; implementers among health system, social care system, CBOs or CSOs.
Common type of output following stage	Description of intervention (theory of change)	Description of intervention (who, where, how) in some cases complemented by theory of change, or intervention mechanism elaboration.	Intervention manual	Scale-up manuals, clinical or operational guidelines	Intervention information embedded in pre-service training and other educational initiatives; intervention embedded in service packages.
Scope of research	Interested stakeholders working together and potentially writing up intervention description.	Studies involving targeted homogenous patient group, with research in 1-2 sites, often one country, small scale studies with small patient numbers prepared by researchers	Research involving more sites of larger size and potentially diverse types (e.g. small vs. large clinics), usually cross-country, larger number of patients involved and usually with heterogeneous characteristics.	Studies of diverse sites of diverse sizes, with heterogeneous populations; in multiple countries, and in diverse types of situations.	Studies, including policy analyses, of intervention adoption and effective means of circumventing barriers to full adoption into systems.

Domain	Ideate	Prototype exemplar	Improve and test	Scale	Adopt
Common description in global literature	Commentary on new intervention opportunity	Proof of concept studies, feasibility trials (; most of these would be without clear control group) and potentially stage 1 trials, hybrid 1 trials.	Implementation studies, effectiveness and implementation trials, hybrid 2 trials. Most of these studies would now incorporate a control or comparator group.	Implementation trials, scale-up studies, hybrid 3 trials. Studies now explicitly incorporate comparators but also waitlist controls.	Adoption studies, hybrid 3 trials

Case Examples

PM+ (Psychological intervention)

Problem Management Plus (PM+) is a manualised intervention targeting individuals with mental disorders including anxiety and depression. It was one of the first 'low intensity' interventions developed by WHO seeking to respond to the mhGAP strategy to strengthen capacity of non-specialists to address mental health disorders⁷.

The table below (Table 2) summarises key studies and initiatives representing the development pipeline for PM+ over the decade since its launch. Ideation was rooted in the needs identified in the formulation of mhGAP, with twenty-four international experts convened to develop a prototype of a five-session intervention package integrating problem-solving and behavioural treatment techniques of established efficacy. Funds were secured for two fully powered RCTs of PM+ in Kenya and Pakistan, with both trials involving extensive adaptation to the cultural contexts of these settings.

On the basis of these studies, Terre des Hommes secured funding to document processes of implementation and adaptation of PM+ in three humanitarian contexts, with the specific remit of identifying barriers and facilitators to scaling. Simultaneously, through the EU-funded STRENGTHS consortium and other initiatives, a number of feasibility and piloting studies began to examine varied mechanisms of delivery of PM+ (e.g. group-based, peer-to-peer, telephone etc.) and its application with differing populations (including with the addition of modules to address specific conditions e.g. regarding alcohol use of emotional processing).

The only published study to date of PM+ cost-effectiveness raised some issues regarding scaling of the intervention and means to reduce its costs. A Special Section of the journal *Intervention* in 2021 then brought together researcher, implementer, policy maker and PWLE views on implementation, with a particular focus on retaining fidelity through processes of adaptation and systems and sustainability issues regarding training and supervision.

By early 2024 the extent of scaling was indicated by a scoping study identifying published reports on PM+ implementation in at least 19 countries (including low-, mid- and high-income settings). While reinforcing the evidence-base regarding efficacy and effectiveness, this reflected the growing awareness of barriers to adoption which have prompted consideration of strategies to reduce the length of the intervention (to reduce costs and human resource needs) while retaining clinical impact.

Nonetheless, significant steps towards adoption have been witnessed, including specification of PM+ in the IASC MHPSS Minimum Service Package in humanitarian emergencies and the recent WHO guidance in integrating PM+ and other evidence-based psychological interventions into existing services. A key factor that has supported use of PM+ has been the existence of a publicly available manual.

7 Ohrmberger, J., Fichera, E., Sutton, M. et al. The effect of cash transfers on mental health – new evidence from South Africa. *BMC Public Health* 20, 436 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-08596-7>

Table 2: PM + example over time

Stage	2015-2016	2017-2018	2019-2020	2021-2022	2023-2024
Ideate	PM+ manual developed through consultation convened by WHO and funded by UNHCR			Formative study of telephone delivery of PM+ with PLWH	
Prototype	Fully powered RCTs demonstrating efficacy and effectiveness conducted in Kenya and Pakistan after cultural adaptation	Feasibility trials of group-based delivery	RCT for Group PM+ in Nepal RCT for peer-to-peer delivery of group-based PM+ in Türkiye	Pilot RCT of Group PM+ in Türkiye Feasibility trials of PM+A (Alcohol) in Uganda, Ukraine, and PM+EP (Emotional Processing) in the Netherlands	Feasibility study with Arabic-speaking migrants in Paris Feasibility trials of impact on stressors
Adapt		elrha fund TdH adaptation work in Ethiopia, Syria and Honduras identifying barriers and facilitating factors to scale up PM+	NIHR fund feasibility study and pilot trial targeting asylum seekers and refugees in UK		Adaptation and feasibility trial of PM+Adherence for adolescents LWH in South Africa
Scale			Only cost-effectiveness study finding PM+ 5-20 times more costly than EUC challenges scaling assumptions	Special Section of Intervention Journal documents experiences of implementing across multiple settings.	Scoping study identifies PM+ implementation across 19 countries
Adopt				PM+ specified in IASC Minimum Service Package for use in all humanitarian emergencies.	WHO issues guidance on integrating PM+ and other evidence-based psychological interventions into existing services

Principal source: Mwangala PN, Makandi M, Kerubo A, Nyongesa MK, Abubakar A. A scoping review of the literature on the application and usefulness of the Problem Management Plus (PM+) intervention around the world. *BJPsych Open*. 2024;10(3):e91. doi:10.1192/bjo.2024.55

Social intervention (Cash transfers)

Cash transfers are one of the most ubiquitous social interventions available to policymakers today when seeking to achieve poverty alleviation. The intervention has rarely been implemented with the primary purpose of targeting mental health outcomes⁸. However, in addressing the alleviation of poverty (an established social determinant of mental health), the intervention can be understood to have potential secondary or tertiary prevention benefits relevant to the scope of this review⁹.

A brief overview of the development of this intervention – described through the lens of the development pipeline – is presented below based on a critical historical anthropological analysis by Fotta and Schmidt¹⁰ and a critical analysis of cash transfer scale-up and adoption during COVID-19¹¹.

Table 3 illustrates – in broad terms – the development of the cash transfer intervention since 1980. As the table suggests, the development pipeline cannot be seamlessly applied in the case of this intervention as multiple stages often coincide and the thresholds for moving between stages are not as strict as those expected in other fields. For example, while CT were recognised as a promising instrument in the 1980s, major randomised trials and implementation studies were not seen until after the 2000s, with most robust evidence generated after 2010 with the support of the World Bank. However, RCTs implicitly focused on testing interventions in a highly controlled environment, despite earlier realisation already from 2000 onward that implementation would differ according to national health systems and their capacity to administer interventions at scale.

Scale-up to all global regions (i.e. with evidence of implementation available across regions) then did happen following 2010, but with important levels of variability in implementation which in practice also led to unintended consequences. For example, Fotta and Schmidt point to the fact that CTs are often introduced in times of social service reduction (including for health) and that agencies administering CTs gain huge power over local populations and resources. This is the case particularly in low-income countries where state mechanisms for CT administration may not be effective.

Following COVID-19, given the well-established evidence for CT, it is not surprising that they were adopting as a means of both compensating for lost income and poverty alleviation. However, despite the evidence base, further investment into research and adaptation of the intervention was still needed – particularly when considering what model of the intervention could be offered at scale in any given context. Gentilini and colleagues (2022) highlighted implementation considerations as the most important when considering whether CT helped achieve intended outcomes and contributed to reducing – or widening – existing inequities. Their work also points to alternative intervention modalities – e.g. protections for unemployed and informal workers, universal designs – as alternatives for CT.

⁸ Owusu-Addo E, Renzaho AMN, Smith BJ. The impact of cash transfers on social determinants of health and health inequalities in sub-Saharan Africa: a systematic review. *Health Policy Plan.* 2018 Jun 1;33(5):675-696. doi: 10.1093/heapol/czy020. PMID: 29762708; PMCID: PMC5951115.

⁹ Ohrnberger, J., Fichera, E., Sutton, M. et al. The effect of cash transfers on mental health – new evidence from South Africa. *BMC Public Health* 20, 436 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-08596-7>

¹⁰ Fotta, Martin, and Mario Schmidt. (2022) 2023. "Cash transfers". In *The Open Encyclopedia of Anthropology*, edited by Felix Stein. Facsimile of the first edition in *The Cambridge Encyclopedia of Anthropology*. Online: <http://doi.org/10.29164/22cashtransfer>

¹¹ Gentilini, U., Almenfi, M., TMM Iyengar, H., Zafar, U., Raul Urteaga, E., Valleriani, G., Aziz, S., & Vulembera, J. (2022). Evidence, Practices, and Implications from the Largest Scale Up in History CASH TRANSFERS IN PANDEMIC TIMES.

Table 3: Cash transfers over time

Stage	1980	1990	2000	2010	2020
Ideate	CT recognised as highly flexible intervention for poverty alleviation (evidence provided by NGO experiments and small pilots)				
Prototype			Desire to see expansion of CT programmes to other settings, but challenges emerge related to weak state administrative infrastructures. Questions arise over whether conditionalities should be introduced and/how; WB endorses intervention, but multiple trials now conducted on alternative models for delivery and management.		
Adapt		Latin American countries adopt CT (usually conditional) in the wake of failed structural adjustment policies; adoption and adaptation into national systems happen simultaneously for many settings, e.g. see Mexico's Progresa.		CT still endorsed by WB as major poverty alleviation mechanism following evidence from multiple trials, but adoption into national systems now sees substantive adaptations for scaling – CT becomes intervention type encompassing multiple mechanisms. These depend on regularity of payment, who makes the payment, conditions imposed and verification of these.	COVID-19 provides huge window of opportunity: expansion to over ¾ of countries globally but without full coverage across population group.
Scale					
Adopt					

Appendix 2: Project team and advisory group

Project Team

Organisation	Role	Person and role	Expertise
IGHD, QMU	Lead	Karin Diaconu	Research focused on complex intervention evaluation and evidence review, including psychosocial interventions.
IGHD, QMU	Experts	Alastair Ager	Mental health (MH) service provision in the UK; evaluation of psychological and social interventions in low- and middle-income settings (LMIC) (led WHO Special Initiative for Mental Health mid-term evaluation); global mental health policy.
IGHD, QMU	Experts	Yasin Duman	Research on MHPSS, evaluation of psychological and social interventions in post-conflict and return settings, (re)integration of refugees and internally displaced persons.
IGHD, QMU	Experts	Kathleen Rutledge	Multi-sectoral programming for response in emergencies, implementation of social interventions, focus on faith/culture and effects on MH.
IGHD, QMU	Experts	Arek Dakessian	Research focused on political alterity, such as refugeedom, and the entwining of the aesthetic and the political.
IGHD, QMU	Research assistant	Aya Noubani	Evidence reviews and evaluation of social interventions for MH.
CASS, QMU	Lead	Olivia Sagan	Professor of Psychology; experience of humanitarian projects including work in psychosocial and psychoeducational interventions, research focuses on the lived experience of mental illness.
CASS, QMU	Research assistant	Mhairi Scally Robertson	Researcher and counselling psychologist.
MHPSS.net	Lead	Ananda Galappatti	MHPSS provision across humanitarian, development and peacebuilding contexts in Sri Lanka; global and local knowledge exchange and networking for LMIC;
MHPSS.net	Expert	Marcio Gagliato	Mental health and psychosocial support service provision in humanitarian settings in LMIC and high-income countries; global and local knowledge exchange and networking for LMIC;
MHPSS.net	Research assistant	Sadhani Rajapakse	Global MH; clinical psychology; search, author engagement and curation of psychological interventions for LMICs and humanitarian settings.

Organisation	Role	Person and role	Expertise
MHPSS.net	Research assistant	Valeria Florez	Global MH; clinical psychology; search, author engagement and curation of psychological interventions for LMICs and humanitarian settings.
MHPSS.net	Research assistant	Ana Molina	Global MH; clinical psychology; search, author engagement and curation of psychological interventions for LMICs and humanitarian settings.

Global Advisory Board Members

Person	WHO Region	Stakeholder Category	Expertise
Charlotte Hanlon	Africa - Ethiopia	Developer/ Evaluator	Chair of Global Mental Health, Deanery of Clinical Sciences, Edinburgh University.
Kaustubh Joag	Southeast Asia - India	Developer/ Evaluator	Consultant psychiatrist and Senior Research Fellow at the Centre for Mental Health Law & Policy, ILS, Pune.
Ottorino Bonvini	Americas (Central and South) - Brazil	Developer/ Implementer	Psychiatrist, Priest, Community Activist, Social movement for mental health.
Rochelle Burgess	Europe - UK	Evaluator/ Developer	Associate Professor in Global Health and Deputy Director of the UCL Centre for Global Non-Communicable Diseases, at the Institute for Global Health at UCL.
Wietse Tol	Europe - Denmark	Evaluator	Professor in Global Mental Health at the Section for Global Health, Department of Public Health, University of Copenhagen, Denmark.
Weeam Hammoudeh	Eastern-Mediterranean - oPt	Evaluator/ Implementer	Assistant Professor at the Institute of Community and Public Health, and coordinator of the mental health unit, Birzeit University, Occupied Palestinian Territories.
Sahil Chopra	Americas (North) - Canada	Funder	Grand Challenges Being Initiative; funds extensive, innovative, locally-led Youth-focussed MH in Colombia, Ecuador, Ghana, India, Indonesia, Morocco, Pakistan, Romania, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Tanzania, and Vietnam.
Prudence Atukunda Friberg	Africa - Ethiopia	Implementer	Senior Thematic Advisor, CBPS, Humanitarian Unit, ACT Alliance; Global Chair of the Psychosocial Support Communities of Practice (PS CoPs) for ACT Alliance.
Agus Hasan Hidayat	South-East Asia - Indonesia	Lived Experience	Disability activist who fights for the rights of youth groups with psychosocial disabilities.
Raj Mariwala	South-East Asia - India	Lived Experience / Funder	Founder of Mariwala Health Initiative, supporting a wide range of social and psychological interventions across India (and beyond).

Person	WHO Region	Stakeholder Category	Expertise
Renet van der Waals	Europe - Netherlands	Policy-maker (Global)	Coordinator Mental Health and Psychosocial Support in crises and Coordinator Ukraine for Stabilisation and Humanitarian Aid Department Ministry of Foreign Affairs.
Jerome Galea	Americas (North) - USA	Policy-maker (Global)	USAID Bureau for Global Health, MHPSS Coordinator has just written the MHPSS Position paper for USAID. Jerome is a licensed clinical social worker and global mental health implementation scientist.
Yuri Cutipe Cardenas	America (Central & South) - Peru	Policy-maker (National)	Former executive director of Mental Health at the Ministry of Health (Minsa) and currently serves as the deputy executive of the ministerial office. Implemented significant mental health reform in Peru.
Crick Lund	Africa - South Africa	Evaluator	Professor of Global Mental Health and Development in the Centre for Global Mental Health, Institute of Psychiatry, Psychology and Neuroscience, King's College London, and Professor in the Alan J. Flisher Centre for Public Mental Health, Department of Psychiatry and Mental Health, University of Cape Town.
Shane Batla	South-East Asia - Thailand	Lived Experience	Self-identifies as queer, trans person of colour (he/they) disabled (psychosocial disability) and chronically ill independent activist and consultant for LGBTIQ+ issues. Former member of ILGA Asia, and associate director of Equal Asia Foundation.
Sandra Ferreira	Africa - South Africa	Lived Experience	Global Manager and Expert by Experience at the Global Mental Health Peer Network.

Appendix 3: Further methodological detail for landscape map

An overarching view of methods used is available in the table below and in the following sections.

Table 4: Methods used for landscape mapping

Element	Purpose	How this was done	Limitations and mitigation approach
Evidence review	Map what is out there globally, relatively well described in literature and that is established; get information on active ingredients, efficacy, effectiveness, populations targeted and geographic reach.	Targeted searches in key bibliographic databases that identified reviews for psychological and social interventions for conditions of interest conducted in the last 10 years; searches of trial registers and key grey literature databases, and websites complemented above.	Large volume of literature meant that screening was conducted individually; there is a chance that important documents were missed, however given the pragmatic aim of mapping interventions and other methods used, we feel confident the impact is minimal. The literature is heterogeneous; as the aim is critical analysis of this body of work, we present key insights rather than detailed analyses of themes and sub-groups.
Digital survey	Ensures further global reach, can help identify what is less likely to be documented formally and which may not be accessible (minimises impact of publication bias inherent in evidence review or social desirability bias inherent in group consultations)	Invited submissions of those who have knowledge – practitioners, developers, implementers, researchers to submit short online survey. Invites were issued to members of the global advisory group, who were asked to send this on; consultation participants were also sent the survey and MHPSS.net sent this to its members. The survey was thus shared via email and online via communities of practice.	The survey was open for one month, but only fifteen responses were gathered. Thirteen of the interventions mentioned were new (not previously captured in the literature) and were incorporated for discussion in consultations; targeted searches for evidence specific to these interventions were also carried out.
Consultations with funders, policy makers, researchers, developers, implementers, and practitioners	Capture stakeholder perspectives on the field and the evidence located from the review and survey; use stakeholder perspectives to complement and add to the information gathered where there are gaps; discuss emerging hypotheses; discuss perspectives on	Consultations across six geographic regions with the defined stakeholder groups. Transcripts and audio recordings of these served as basis of a thematic analysis. Where possible stakeholder insights were used to complement the evidence review.	Eleven stakeholder consultations were convened across diverse time zones. Consultations were region specific and representation from all regions was achieved, but there were difficulties in recruiting participants from specific groups (e.g. developers were only minimally represented). Overall, despite

Element	Purpose	How this was done	Limitations and mitigation approach
	the evidence and barriers and opportunities for advancing in this field – what is holding up development, implementation, scale-up; identify where stakeholders think investment is needed to advance field		the brief time frame for consultations (3 weeks), we are confident that saturation across all participant groups was achieved. Phase 2 offers opportunities to select more specific stakeholders for further interviews/consultation.
Consultations with PLE	Capture PLE perspectives on conditions and interventions available, identify missed opportunities; identify levels of involvement in development, implementation, scaling etc. and perceptions around effectiveness (and what this means for PLE and whether/how interventions meet needs);	The research team put out a call for expressions of interest for PLE led organisations across all six WHO regions. A briefing webinar explaining the project and reviewing consultation tools and methods was organised. Organisations had the chance to formally apply for conducting consultations with diverse PLE groups. Based on the expressions of interest 4 PLE-led organisations carried out consultations involving a total of 32 participants across 3 WHO Regions (SEARO, AFRO, WPRO). Each organisation consulted a different demographic providing diverse views to the study. Organisations were required to submit relevant consent forms, a summary of the consultation and audio recordings. All organisations were then remunerated for their effort.	Four PLE-led organisations were selected to convene. Two of the organisations were based in the AFRO region and one each in the SEARO region and WPRO region. Unfortunately, despite repeated attempts to recruit from the other regions – PAHO, EURO and EMRO – we were not able to secure engagement of PLE led organisations here. The ongoing conflict in the Middle East is likely the main reason for disengagement in EMRO. We propose re-attempting engagement across the three non-sampled regions in Phase 2.

Evidence review

Searches of bibliographic databases identified 12,959 records which underwent further screening (see Figure 3 for details). The team screened titles for relevance, retaining those documents directly referring to the target conditions of interest (depression, anxiety, and psychosis) and excluded titles that clearly referenced pharmacological or digital interventions. Following this, 3,373 abstracts were read, with 328 full texts prioritised for full text review. 205 documents were then retained for inclusion in the review following application of a further set of exclusion criteria (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: PRISMA diagram

The documents retained were systematic reviews which focused on comparing key interventions with one another, including either narrative summaries or meta-analyses. Comparisons were predominantly conducted against treatment as usual. Data from all reviews was extracted with support of an AI programme (SciSpace AI) and then cross-checked by a member of the research team. Individual researchers were then responsible for quality assessing each of the reviews and noting the certainty of evidence associated with findings discussed in reviews.

We extracted data from all reviews on key variables (as specified in the inception report) and proceeded in a systematic stepwise fashion.

- 1. Identifying interventions:** For this step, we first classified all reviews against a target condition, focusing on sub-conditions where relevant (e.g. bipolar disorder, schizophrenia). Once this was done, we analysed the extracted data and identified the interventions that were discussed across the literature. We then listed all these and assigned them to a category (psychological, psychosocial, or social).
- 2. Mapping information:** Once we had the full list of interventions available, we proceeded to more deeply analyse data by target condition. This means that for each target condition and intervention combination, we mapped out the types of evidence that were available, what populations the intervention had been studied in and in what settings.

Regarding types of evidence, we focused specifically on distinguishing aspects of efficacy, effectiveness, cost-effectiveness and lived experience. One study could refer to multiple aspects and would be mapped against these as appropriate.

For populations, we focused on identifying whether evidence was available for specific subpopulations. For example, we considered how populations were characterised across literature by age groups:

- 4.** children (up to age of 10), adolescents (10-19) and young people (up to 25),
- 5.** adults – many reviews focused on those over 18, but where relevant we considered the median age referenced, and if the majority of evidence referred to persons over 25 and under 65 we classified this as referring to adults.
- 6.** elderly populations (over 65).

We also considered whether reviews mentioned specific populations who are at increased risk of developing depression, anxiety, and psychosis – for example, refugees and migrants or women post-partum. Where relevant we comment on these populations.

Further, we considered which countries the interventions and studies described across reviews had taken place. We then categorised countries according to the 2023 World Bank income classification and generated graphics that showcased locations evidence referred to.

- 1. Critical analysis:** Following the above, we generated graphics summarising the landscape for the psychological, psychosocial, and social intervention categories. We prepared narrative summaries accompanying the graphics, which highlight key insights from the main themes represented across the literature and evidence gaps. Where relevant, information from the stakeholder consultations is also integrated.

Stakeholder perspectives of the field

We successfully convened eleven virtual stakeholder consultations across multiple time zones. These engaged sixteen funders, developers, or evaluators; eleven implementers, practitioners, and policymakers; and 3 persons with lived experience (insights from this latter stakeholder group were more fully elicited from the 4 consultations with organisations representing persons with lived experience reported in the next section). We met with persons based in all WHO regions, although stakeholders frequently commented on their experience working in other regions.

PLE perspectives of the field

The principal mode of eliciting PLE perspectives was through a call to PLE-led organisations to facilitate consultations in relation to experience of receiving – and engaging in the development of - psychological or social interventions. PLE organisations were asked to specifically identify people with experience of the target conditions of interest (see Table 5).

Four PLE-led organisations were selected to convene these consultations (see participants in Table 5), which followed a common format established through an orientation workshop. Two of the organisations were based in the AFRO region and one each in the SEARO region and WPRO region. Additionally, two representatives of PLE-led organisations from the SEARO region were engaged in the wider stakeholder consultation process. There is potential to further extend involvement with PLE from other regions in the second phase of this project.

Table 5: Participants in consultations

Region	Nr.	Description
SEARO	8	Participants with perinatal mood and anxiety disorders such as postnatal depression, anxiety disorders and psychosis
AFRO	13	Participants from two organisations. 1. Members of PLE support group forums for mental health conditions 2. Counsellors with lived experience of anxiety and depression
WPRO	11	Participants with lived experience of mental health conditions.

Appendix 4: Priority-setting using Delphi like process

A draft version of the landscape mapping report together with all annexes documenting the landscape analysis of interventions for the targeted mental health conditions was circulated to members of the Global Advisory Board. GAB members were then invited to join one of four workshops to reflect on the content of the report, specifically the overview of interventions and reflections of stakeholders and PLE and engage in a consensus prioritisation exercise.

In these workshops, GAB members reviewed the list of agreed prioritisation criteria (see Table 6) shared at the outset of the project. Connections between these criteria and findings highlighted in the report from the consultations were noted where relevant. GAB members were then taken through three matrices summarising the findings of the landscape analysis (broadly grouped as psychological, social, or psychosocial interventions), with the level of ‘pipeline development’ for each intervention summarised with respect to relevant target conditions. On the basis of the specified prioritisation criteria and these landscape analysis summaries, GAB members were invited to cast five votes for further exploration of interventions listed in each of the three summaries. Members could allocate all their votes to one intervention (indicating strong preference for the intervention and then supporting an argument for why it should be prioritised) or divide their votes among the diverse interventions.

Following this independent casting of votes, GAB members were asked to explain their selections with respect to the summarised evidence-base and relevant prioritisation criteria. In discussion, GAB members could choose if/where to revise votes.

Table 6: Prioritisation criteria

Domain	Criteria
Clinical evidence	Clear mechanistic understanding or rationale of how the intervention works (practitioners, researchers)
Clinical evidence	Clear understanding or rationale of whom the intervention works for exists (practitioners, researchers)
Clinical evidence	Efficacy and/or effectiveness is high, or potential is high (practitioners, researchers)
Relevance to PLE	Meet the needs and priorities of end beneficiaries (as defined by PLE)
Relevance to PLE	Be developed in collaboration with people with lived experience (PLE)
Context, applicability and scalability	Include clear and scalable routes to implementation whether by industry or other stakeholders (as defined by implementers/practitioners, policy makers)
Context, applicability and scalability	Be capable of being applied at scale in low resource settings (as defined by policy makers and researchers)
Context, applicability and scalability	Efficiency and/or cost-effectiveness is highly desirable or there is potential (researchers)

Domain	Criteria
Context, applicability and scalability	Be applicable even in the context of challenging global events such as extreme heat, other extreme weather events, future pandemics, mass migration, international conflict, conflict between social groups and lack of trust in science (all) (as defined by policy makers and researchers)
Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity, and inclusion	Intervention has potential to reduce inequalities – in country or globally (all)
Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity, and inclusion	Scale of unmet need (all)

Senior members of the project team replicated this process, and the results pooled to create a prioritised listing of interventions for further analysis in phase 2 of the work. Interventions are recommended for further analysis if they received three or more nominations through this process.

Additionally, senior members of the project team independently reviewed information on interventions that had been nominated for further analysis during consultations but had not been captured in the landscape analysis, given the primary reliance on systematic reviews. Interventions independently endorsed by two or more senior members of the project team were added to the proposed list for further analysis.

Appendix 5: Pipeline progression by target conditions

Please note that many interventions were simultaneously assessed for efficacy and effectiveness in relation to both depression and/or anxiety. Unless specific types of these disorders were mentioned, we therefore refer to a combination category - depression and/or anxiety.

Psychological interventions

Progression from ideation to other stages*	Prototype exemplar	Improve and test	Scale	Adopt
BPD (n=6)	100%	67%	17%	0%
Depression and/or anxiety (n=13)	100%	85%	54%	23%
PTSD (n=5)	100%	80%	40%	0%
OCD (n=9)	100%	56%	22%	22%
Psychosis (not specified further, n=6)	100%	83%	67%	50%
Schizophrenia (n=5)	100%	60%	20%	0%

*where n refers to number of interventions

Progression from one stage to next	Ideate	Prototype exemplar	Improve and test	Scale	Adopt
BPD (n=6)	100%	67%	25%	0%	0%
Depression and/or anxiety (n=13)	100%	85%	64%	43%	0%
PTSD (n=5)	100%	80%	50%	0%	0%
OCD (n=9)	100%	56%	40%	100%	0%
Psychosis (not specified further, n=6)	100%	83%	80%	75%	0%
Schizophrenia (n=5)	100%	60%	33%	0%	0%

*where n refers to number of interventions

Psychosocial interventions

Progression from ideation to other stages*	Prototype exemplar	Improve and test	Scale	Adopt
BPD (n=4)	100%	50%	0%	0%
Depression and/or anxiety (n=11)	100%	36%	0%	0%
PTSD (n=10)	100%	50%	0%	0%
Schizophrenia (n=6)	100%	83%	17%	0%

*where n refers to number of interventions

Progression from one stage to next*	Ideate	Prototype exemplar	Improve and test	Scale	Adopt
BPD (n=4)	100%	50%	0%	0%	0%
Depression and/or anxiety (n=11)	100%	36%	0%	0%	0%
PTSD (n=10)	100%	50%	0%	0%	0%
Schizophrenia (n=6)	100%	83%	17%	0%	0%

*where n refers to number of interventions

Social interventions

Progression from ideation to other interventions	Prototype exemplar	Improve and test	Scale	Adopt
BPD (n=1)	100%	100%	0%	0%
Depression and/or anxiety (n=9)	67%	44%	0%	0%
Psychosis (n=7)	57%	14%	0%	0%
Schizophrenia (n=1)	100%	100%	0%	0%
Serious mental illness (n=1)	100%	100%	0%	0%

*where n refers to number of interventions

Progression from one stage to next	Ideate	Prototype exemplar	Improve and test	Scale	Adopt
BPD (n=1)	100%	100%	0%	0%	0%
Depression and/or anxiety (n=9)	67%	67%	0%	0%	0%
Psychosis (n=7)	57%	25%	0%	0%	0%
Schizophrenia (n=1)	100%	100%	0%	0%	0%
Serious mental illness (n=1)	100%	100%	0%	0%	0%

*where n refers to number of interventions

Appendix 6: Overview of psychological, psychosocial, and social interventions against priority setting criteria